

Subject: Research Idea Submission - Thermal Energy Storage for Space & Remote Applications

My name is Shower Mohamed, an independent researcher in mechanical/thermal engineering. I would like to submit a concept for review regarding thermal energy storage via daytime overcooling as an alternative to batteries.

Concept:

Use solar energy during the day to overcool insulated storage units. High-grade insulation maintains the low temperature overnight without power input. This reduces weight, cost, and maintenance compared to batteries.

The approach is suitable for polar stations, lunar bases, and Mars missions where battery mass and lifespan are critical constraints.

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